

Studies in Terpenes. Part XXXI: Sylveterpinolene and Isosylveterpinolene

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***m*-Mentha-1(2),3(8)-diene (sylveterpinolene) (II) and *m*-mentha-1(6), 3(8)-diene (isosylveterpinolene) (III) have been isolated and characterised from the dehydrohalogenate derived from *d*-sylvestrene dihydrochloride (I). With hydrogen halides, these hydrocarbons furnished *dl*-sylvestrene dihydrohalides. Reactions of sylveterpinolene with maleic anhydride, 20% phosphoric acid and 10% palladium catalyst and of isosylveterpinolene with bromine to afford tetrabromide (IV), m.p. 128°, have been described.**

An excellent source of *m*-menthadienes is the dehydrohalogenate originating from *d*-sylvestrene dihydrochloride (I).¹⁻⁶ We wish to report the isolation and study of the chemistry of two of the hydrocarbons, viz., *m*-mentha-1(2),3(8)-diene (sylveterpinolene) (II) and *m*-mentha-1(6),3(8)-diene (isosylveterpinolene) (III).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the directions of Chabudzinski⁴, elimination of hydrogen chloride from (I) generated an oil consisting of at least five components (GLC). Precise fractionation of the oil at 20 mm. afforded a cut, b.p. 85–88°, and this was split further into eight fractions (F₁–F₈), of which our interest centered on F₈, b.p. 88°, (α)_D²⁰ ± 0° and F₈, b.p. 87–88°, (α)_D²⁰ ± 0°.

Fraction F₈, designated as sylveterpinolene, shown to be homogeneous by GLC, was characterised as (II) by analytical and spectral data: cf.⁷ UV λ_{max}^{EtOH} 244 m μ (log ϵ 4.303) (conjugated diene); IR $\gamma_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 1620 cm⁻¹ (conjugated diene); NMR (CCl₄): τ 8.09 (s, 9H, 3-CH₃), 3.93 (s, C₂-H).

Sylveterpinolene exhibited intense methylene blue colouration in Wallach's test.^{3,2} Addition of hydrogen halides furnished inactive sylvestrene dihydrohalides and of maleic anhydride, an adduct, m.p. 306–308° (lit.⁵ 304–308°). With a view to assessing the stability of (II), we examined the response of the hydrocarbon to 20% aq. phosphoric acid. Reaction with the acid at ~100° yielded four components which included 1.2% (III) and 85.7% (II), the latter further confirmed by adduction with maleic anhydride. The presence of such a high proportion of (II) testified to its stability under the experimental conditions. Finally, disproportionation of (II) gave a catalysate, comprising essentially of *m*-cymene and *m*-menthane(s), in accordance with the equation: $3C_{10}H_{16} \rightarrow 2C_{10}H_{14} + C_{10}H_{20}$.

* Taken in part from the Ph.D. Thesis of N. V. M., University of Madras (1970).

Fraction F₃ consisted of (II) and another hydrocarbon, isosylveterpinolene (III), (35.2%, GLC). By reaction with maleic anhydride, (II) was substantially eliminated to give enriched (III) [93.76% (GLC)]. Its bromination yielded 1,3,6,8-tetrabromo-*m*-menthane (IV), m.p. 127–128°, NMR (CDCl₃) : τ 7.87 (s, 9H, 3-CH₃), 7.75–6.67 (m, 6H, 3-CH₂) and 5.08 (C₆-H). Obviously, the parent hydrocarbon of the tetrabromide is (III) to which it was reverted completely by debromination with zinc, b.p. 87–88°/20 mm., IR (CHCl₃) : 1680, 1449, 830, 790 cm⁻¹ (tri-substituted double bond), NMR (CDCl₃) : τ 8.35 (s, 9H, 3-CH₃) 7.87 (s, C₄, C₅-4H), 7.40 (broad, s, C₂-2H) and 4.63 (m, C₆-H).

Isosylveterpinolene, hitherto unreported in literature, is a colourless oil with smell reminiscent of sylvestrene, showing like sylveterpinolene, in Wallach's test, intense methylene blue colouration. When hydrohalogenated and brominated, (III) furnished dl-sylvestrene dihydrohalides and tetrabromide (IV) respectively. The incorporation of the elements of hydrogen halides, parallel to that of (II), merit special emphasis in as much as they resulted in disylvestrene derivatives. Clearly then, dl-sylvestrene dihydrohalides can be derived from various double bond isomers.

EXPERIMENTAL

M.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. IR : Perkin-Elmer 221; GLC : Column, SE 30 on Aerograph A-90 P3 model. NMR : 60 MHz with TMS as internal reference standard. Optical rotations were recorded in CHCl₃. Other details have been reported*.

m-Menthadienes : The procedure of Chabudzinski⁴ was followed. Gentle heating of *d*-sylvestrene dihydrochloride (100 g.) and aniline (150 g.) and work-up afforded a mixture of *m*-menthadienes (50.6 g., 77.73%), n_D^{20} 1.4841, d_{30}^{30} 0.8431, $(\alpha)_D^{30} +45.10^\circ$, five components : 23.2, 49.5, 2.3, 12.5 and 12.5% (GLC), having the following boiling ranges (20 mm.) : (a) 69–70°, 56.0%, n_D^{20} 1.4735, d_{30}^{30} 0.8373, $(\alpha)_D^{30} +80.69^\circ$; (b) 77–85°, 13.9%, n_D^{20} 1.4837, d_{30}^{30} 0.8455, $(\alpha)_D^{30} +40.94^\circ$; (c) 85–88°, 26.2%, n_D^{20} 1.5063, d_{30}^{30} 0.8634, $(\alpha)_D^{30} +1.31^\circ$. Precise redistillation of (c) at 20 mm. and reflux ratio 50 : 1 gave two fractions : F₈, 7.3%, b.p. 88°, n_D^{20} 1.5145, d_{30}^{30} 0.8692, $(\alpha)_D^{30} \pm 0^\circ$ and F₃, 6.4%, b.p. 87–88°, n_D^{20} 1.5074, d_{30}^{30} 0.8612, $(\alpha)_D^{30} \pm 0^\circ$.

Sylveterpinolene viz., fraction F₈, GLC : single peak. Found : C, 87.52; H, 11.78. C₁₀H₁₆ requires C, 88.23; H, 11.77%; UV, IR and NMR as described earlier; Wallach's test³ : intense methylene blue colour.

(a) *Hydrochlorination* : Passed a current of hydrogen chloride into a solution of (II) (10 g.) in ether (~ 36 ml.) cooled to below -5° for 8–9 hr.; the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight in the cold and then extracted with ether. Normal work-up afforded a clear oil, b.p. 136–140°/20 mm. which upon chilling solidified to a white mass; dl-sylvestrene dihydrochloride (1.45 g.), m.p. 53° (from methanol), lit.⁸ 52.5°; $(\alpha)_D^{30} \pm 0^\circ$; NMR (CCl₄) : τ 8.45 (s, 6H, 2-CH₃), 8.37 (s, 3H, -CH₃). Found : C, 57.3; H, 8.4; Cl, 33.6. C₁₀H₁₆Cl₂ requires C, 57.4; H, 8.7; Cl, 33.9%.

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(b) *Hydrobromination* : A stream of hydrogen bromide was bubbled for 9 hr. through a solution of (II) (13.8 g.) in ether (\sim 32 ml.) chilled to below -5° . Recrystallisation of the precipitate from methanol gave dl-sylvestrene dihydrobromide (10.3 g.) : m.p. $48-49^\circ$, lit.⁸ $48-50^\circ$, (α) $\frac{D}{D} \pm 0^\circ$. Found : Br, 53.11. $C_{10}H_{18}Br_2$ requires Br, 53.65%.

(c) *Maleic anhydride adduction* : Sylveterpinolene (2.1 g.), maleic anhydride (3.04 g.) and acetone (5 ml.) were reacted following the procedure described for α -phellandrene⁹ to give white flakes of the crude adduct. Double precipitation from acetone solution with methanol gave an analytical sample (3.56 g.) : m.p. $306-308^\circ$ (decomp.). Found : C, 71.07; H, 7.62. $C_{14}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 71.78; H, 7.74%.

(d) *Action of 20% aq. phosphoric acid* : A mixture of (II) (15.1 g.) and 20% aq. phosphoric acid was stirred (magnet bar) under reflux for 20 hr. at $102-103^\circ$. The steam volatile oil from the reaction mixture indicated in GLC four components : (a) 12.2, (b) 1.0, (c) 1.2 and (d) 85.7%, (c) and (d) corresponding to (III) and (II) respectively. Precise fractionation of the oil (10 g.) at 20 mm. and reflux ratio 50 : 1 gave two cuts : (1) b.p. $64-77^\circ$, 9.8%, n_D^{20} 1.4888; (2) b.p. $85-88^\circ$, 76.1%, n_D^{20} 1.5126. Fraction (2) (5.2 g.) afforded maleic anhydride adduct (\sim 730 mg.), m.p. and mixed m.p. $306-308^\circ$ (decomp.).

(e) *Disproportionation* : Heated under reflux (II) (7.83 g.) and 10% Pd catalyst (0.76 g.) for 10 hr. at $140 \pm 2^\circ$. Recovery gave a colourless oil (6.6 g.), b.p. $168-169^\circ/737.5$ mm., n_D^{20} 1.4732, d_{30}^{30} 0.8324, analysed by GLC to contain *m*-cymene (63.4%) and *m*-menthane(s) (33.7%).

Oxidation of an aliquot portion (0.34 g.) with $K_2Cr_2O_7-H_2SO_4$ mixture gave isophthalic acid (0.22 g.), equivalent to \sim 74.5% *m*-cymene¹⁰. By allowing the catalysate (3.3 g.) to react in the cold with 20% fuming sulphuric acid (25 ml.), *m*-menthane(s) was isolated as a colourless liquid (0.54 g.), b.p. $160-162^\circ/740$ mm., n_D^{20} 1.4424, [lit.¹¹ dl-*m*-menthane, b.p. $167^\circ/760$ mm., n_D^{20} 1.4410; cis-*m*-menthane, n_D^{20} 1.4407; trans-*m*-menthane, n_D^{20} 1.4433].

Isosylvesterpine : (a) *Isolation* : Fraction F_3 (21.46 g.), maleic anhydride (31.2 g.) and acetone (51.50 ml.) were processed as described above and basified with 10% potassium hydroxide; steam distillation afforded a colourless oil (4 g.), n_D^{20} 1.4881, (α) $\frac{D}{D} \pm 0^\circ$, and it was identified as a mixture of (III) (93.7%) and (II) (6.3%) by GLC.

(b) *Bromination* : Preparation of tetrabromide (IV) : A solution of the above oil (2.7 g.) in amyl alcohol (3 ml.) and ether (\sim 6 ml.) was cooled to below -5° . The solution was stirred vigorously and chilled bromine added dropwise so as to maintain the solution reddish brown. Derivative precipitated after cooling 2 hr. was filtered off, washed with ice cold methanol to yield 2.8 g., m.p. 123° and purified from chloroform solution by addition of $CHCl_3$ to give an analytical sample, (2.5 g.), m.p. $127-128^\circ$ (decomp.), (α) $\frac{D}{D} \pm 0^\circ$. Found : Br, 69.85. $C_{10}H_{16}Br_4$ requires Br, 70.18%. NMR spectrum as described earlier.

(c) *Conversion to tetrabromide (IV) to isosylvesterpine (III)* : The tetrabromide (10 g.) dissolved in ether (\sim 123 ml.) and absolute alcohol (38 ml.) was debrominated with zinc dust (14 g.) adopting a former procedure¹² to give (III) (2.6 g.), GLC : single peak, b.p.

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/20 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4882 and $(\alpha)_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$. Found : C, 87.79; H, 11.89. $C_{10}H_{16}$ requires 23; H, 11.77%. IR and NMR spectra as described earlier.

d) *Hydrochlorination* : Reaction of (III) (2.2 g.) dissolved in ether (~ 7 ml.) with hydrogen chloride as for sylveterpinolene afforded dl-sylvestrene dihydrochloride (~ 500 mg.), and mixed m.p. 53° .

e) *Hydrobromination* : The hydrobromination of (III) (1.4 g.) dissolved in (~ 3 ml.) gave dl-sylvestrene dihydrobromide (~ 750 mg.), m.p. and cross 8-49°

f) *Bromination* : Bromination of (III) (100 mg) in amyl alcohol (0.2 ml) and ether (0.2 ml.) furnished the tetrabromide derivative (~ 175 mg.), m.p. and cross m.p. 128° (mp.).

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